

Proposed Social Marketing Campaign to Increase Blood Donation and Active Users in Reblood Application (Case Study: PT Gaya Hidup Sehat)

Putu Linda Primandari Ambarini¹, Iriawan Ibarat²

^{1,2} School of Business and Management, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Every five second, people in Indonesia needs blood. Blood donation is essential in every country to helps patients survive from illnesses and injuries. Indonesia Red Cross (PMI) has released the data of blood donation in 2020, there were 3,5 million blood bags has collected across Indonesia. With current situation, Indonesia still needs to fulfil minimum 5,2 million blood bags (2% of the Indonesian population) per year. Those condition that motivate PT Gaya Hidup Sehat to take a part to solve the problem of shortage blood donors by implementing the healthcare technology with Reblood application. Reblood aimed to provide all of information related with blood donation that currently still limited, not accessible and not integrating each other's. Since it first launched in 2018 until now, Reblood has acquired 60,748 active users with more than 40,000 blood donations collected and transferred to PMI. However, in 2020 until 2021 the number of active users has decreased significantly almost 70% due to pandemic Covid-19. This research was conducted to increase Reblood's active users and encourage more people to do blood donation in order to fulfill blood bags capacity. 337 respondents was participating on the survey to analyze the motivation, barriers, and knowledge and behavior to do blood donation. The result of those analysis then formulate using Social Marketing Framework by Philip Kotler and Nancy R.Lee. The findings in this research enriches the strategy of behavioral changes with the use of social marketing approach for increasing blood donation campaign.

KEYWORDS: Blood donation. Behavior changes, Barriers, Knowledge, Motivation, Social marketing.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia Red-Cross (PMI) has released the data of blood donation in 2020, there were 3,5 million blood bags has collected across Indonesia, even though the number has increased from last year (15%), Indonesia still needs to fulfil minimum 5,2 million blood bags (2% of the Indonesian population) per year as a state by World Health Organization (WHO) [1]. Various strategies have considered by PMI and Ministry for promoting and acquiring blood donors in Indonesia. Most of the program were utilizing the digital platform. For instance, PMI has released official website (<https://pmi.or.id/>) to spread information regarding blood donation that equipped with helpful tools to search and reserve blood donation program across cities, however the result is not significantly impact.

The lack number of blood donation in Indonesia, conversely with the rise of Indonesia population. Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) has released Indonesian population census in 2020, which is dominated by young generation (millennials & Gen Z) with total number of millennial is 69,38 million or contribute 25,87% from the total population [2]. Indonesia is currently experiencing a demographic bonus.

Those condition that motivates PT Gaya Hidup Sehat to take a part to solve the problem of shortage blood donors by implementing the healthcare technology with Reblood application. Reblood is based on mobile app that designed with features that consist of finding blood donation location and schedule, a reminder to do regular blood donation, finding nearest PMI and number of blood inventory for each branch, crowdfunding program, health article, and information. Reblood aimed to provide all of information related with blood donation that currently still limited, not accessible and not integrating each other's. The application is designed very user friendly and follow the technology trends to approach more productive / young generation for being blood donors. Since it first launched in 2018 until now, Reblood has acquired 60,748 active users with more than 40,000 blood donations collected and transferred to PMI. However, the contribution for Reblood were not sufficient and optimal to fulfil minimum numbers of blood bags needed in Indonesia.

To achieve the goal to increase blood donors as well with Reblood's active users, author conduct this research by understanding and define factors that motivate and constraint people to do blood donation using social marketing approach that introduced by Philip Kotler and Nancy R.Lee.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Marketing Campaign

Social marketing has been known widely to promote social change for individual and society benefits. Lots of social marketing campaign have successfully implemented, especially in the health field. Social Marketing seeks to develop and integrate marketing concepts with other approaches to influence behaviours that benefit individuals and communities for the greater social good (Nancy R. Lee, Michael L. Rothschild, and Bill Smith, 2011).

social marketing are integrating many characteristic common to other forms of behaviour change.

There are four core unique principles in Social marketing concept (Philip Kotler and Nancy R.Lee, 2020): value exchange, recognition of competition, the 4P’s of marketing, and sustainability.

Social Marketing Planning. According to Kotler and Lee, there are 10 step of social marketing planning model (Philip Kotler and Nancy R.Lee, 2020) :

1. Describe Social Issue, Organization, background, Purpose and Focus
2. Conduct a Situation Analysis (SWOT)
3. Select Priority Audiences
4. Set Behaviour Objective and Target Goals
5. Identify Priority Audience Insight (Barriers, Benefits, Motivators, Competition and Influential Others)
6. Develop Positioning Statement
7. Develop Strategic Marketing Intervention Mix (4Ps)
8. Plan for Monitoring and Evaluation
9. Budget
10. Plan for Implementation and Sustaining Behaviours

Consumer Behavior

Consumer buyer behaviour is considered to be an inseparable part of marketing and Kotler and Keller (2011) state that consumer buying behaviour is the study of the ways of buying and disposing of goods, services, ideas or experiences by the individuals, groups and organizations in order to satisfy their needs and wants.

Figure 1. Model of Consumer's Behaviour by Kottler and Keller (2006)

RESEARCH METHOD

The method is divide based on research gaps and research questions. To answer research question 1 regarding the factors that motivate people to do blood donation, method that will implement are literature review and in depth analysis on related framework. Quantitative method by conducting survey will be implement on this research. To answer question 2 and 3, qualitative method by interviewing Reblood’s management and literature review regarding social marketing framework by Philip & Kotler and the consumer behaviour model.

Table 1. Research Methodology

Research Gaps	Research Questions & Objectives	Method
Lack of identification and understanding of factors that affect low number of user acquisition & active user of Reblood application	(Q1) What are the factors that motivate people to do blood donation and actively using Reblood application ?	1) Literature Review and analysis of Consumer Behaviour Model by Kotler & Keller 2) Quantitative data collection: Survey to 100 people in Surabaya & Jabodetabek area
Lack of understanding of the potential use of social marketing approach to increase Reblood's active users	(Q2) What are the social marketing program that will implement to increase the Reblood's active users?	1) Literature Review & In-depth Analysis : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal : VRIO , STP, and Marketing mix 4Ps ● External : PESTEL , consumer behavior analysis ● SWOT 2) Qualitative : Reblood's management team interview 3) Literature Review & In-depth Analysis : - Marketing Mix 7ps - Social Marketing framework by Philip Kotler & Nancy R.Lee
	(Q3) How can social marketing approach be applied to increase the Reblood's active users ?	

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

According to the survey, out of 337 respondents, the majority were aged between 20-35 years old (80.1%) and followed by those who are aged 36-50 years old (12.2%). These results indicated that the respondents are mostly millennials and Gen X.

The domicile of the respondent that used in this study is limited to the Jabodetabek and Surabaya areas. From the results obtained, most of the respondents came from Surabaya (65.6%), followed by respondents from Jakarta (18.1%) and Tangerang (7.4%).

There were several factors that motivates someone to donate blood, it shown that humanitarian action is the first most important factor that motivate people do blood donation. In the second place, there is healthy lifestyle reason, most of the respondents realize how important it is to keep their body healthy in this pandemic era. In the third place, there is someone I know is urgently needed. In line with the importance of humanitarian action. And rewards/incentives become the fourth rank, it seems because blood donation enthusiasts will usually be more and more if there are rewards/incentives that we can get after taking blood donation actions. Campaign or advertisement is social media not significantly affecting the behavior as well with the force from the environment.

Table 2. Evaluation of Motivation Variables

Variables of Motivation	Score
Humanitarian action	4,4
Implements a healthy lifestyle	4,2
Someone I know is in urgently needed	3,6
Rewards/ Incentive	3,2
campaign/advertisement in social media	3,0
force from environment	2,7
famous person/ influencer	2,3

On the other hand, there were also some barriers that impacting people fear to donate their blood. It explains that the health concern becoming the first most important factor because it indicates that most of the respondents sometimes not eligible to donate their blood. In the second place, there is fear of contagion. A few of the respondents were curious about the impact after donating blood. In the third place, respondents said fear of needles/pain becomes one of the factors that make them not donate blood. Follow by poor attitude of staff, fear of blood, data privacy breach, lack of information and absence of incentive. It is necessary to take an action that can change the mindset of people especially for teenagers to realize that a bag of blood can save a person's life and when they donate they will get inner satisfaction because it can save other lives.

Table 3. Summary of Potential Barriers

Variables of Barriers	Score
Health concern (does not meet the requirements to donate)	2,6
Fear of contagion	2,1
Fear of needles/pain	2,0
Poor attitude of staff	2,0
Fear of blood	1,9
Data privacy breach	1,9
Lack of information	1,8
Absence of incentives	1,8

The data obtained that as much as 50.7% of them said they are using the Reblood application. Meanwhile, 49.3% said they are not using Reblood apps. It means a few of them find it very helpful with the Reblood application to make it easier for them to remember the blood donation schedule, and other interesting features that are useful for them.

Proposed Segmentation and Targeting Audiences

In order to construct an effective social marketing strategy, market segmentation needs to define into the smaller segment that have similar needs, wants, desire and interest. In this step, the author rebuilt existing segmentation and added analysis based on surveys that were conducted to 337 respondents. The new proposed segmentation for Reblood is illustrated as follows.

Table 4. Proposed New STP

Segmentation	Propose Segmentation
Demographic	<p>Gender : All gender (Female & Male)</p> <p>Age : 17 - 40 years old (Millenials and Gen-Z population)</p> <p>Occupation : University students, fresh graduate, working experience, entrepreneur, housewives, retired, unemployee</p>
Geographic	Jawa Timur and Jabodetabek area.
Psychographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● People with Physically and mentally health ● Health enthusiast people ● People who has big solidarity and willing to help other people ● People who are brave with needle and blood ● People who familiar and accustomed with technology ● Activists

Segmentation	Propose Segmentation
Behavioral	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Needs and benefits : Reblood app users are the people who are the blood donors whether actively or first timer, aware with the benefit of blood donors both for them and society, health enthusiast, activist, and emergency used for people that urgently need blood transfusion ● Occasion : Reblood app could be used for everyday occasion based on users needs ● User status : People who actively and regularly donate their blood , first time blood donors, and people who hesitate to donate. ● Readiness Stage : Unaware, aware, informed, desirous, and intending to do blood donation ● Loyalty Status : First time blood donor , repeat donors and people who never donate.
Personality	Fearless, Humanist, Active, empathy
Lifestyle	Healthy enthusiast, tech-savvy, social awareness, well educated

Develop Positioning Statement

Positioning principles and processes for social marketing are similar to those of commercial marketing. The result of positioning is the successful creation of a user focused and used company product in order to influence them to change their habits. With the profile of priority audience, including any unique demographic, geographic, behavior related, and the research of perceived motivation, barriers, benefits, it will help to craft a positioning statement [5]

In this research, author define audience positioning based on blood donation frequency. There were 3 types of users : First timer, Repeat, and Dormant/ Never donors.

Table 2. Proposed New Positioning for Reblood

Audience Profile	Value Proposition	Proposed Campaign
Dormant/ Never donor	Reblood is an app to help people build healthy lifestyle and saving lives, starting with blood donation	Reveal myth in blood donation, Educated content how to do blood donation, tips to overcome fear, Invitation to start healthy lifestyle, Benefits of Blood donation, welcoming message
First Timer	A donation of blood means a few minutes to you, but a lifetime for somebody else. Check the available schedule on Reblood	Healthy life challenges, Reveal myths, infografis stock of blood bags, post blood emergency needed, Reblood app benefit, Q&A with the expert, blood event information, Reblood personal assistance, rewards information
Repeat	Appreciation for giving someone another life through your blood. Check your lifesaver journey and get your reward in Reblood	Community gathering, Q&A and sharing session with experts, thank you message, rewards information, loyalty program offers

Develop Strategic Marketing Intervention Mix (4Ps)

Product

According to the survey that conducted by author, from 337 respondents, only 166 of them who are familiar and using reblood application. Those 166 users are consists of first timer and repeat users. From that case, it is important for Reblood to improve the product based on behavior objectives and audience proposition that has been described before. (Philip Kotler and Nancy R.Lee, 2020) in their book explained that in social marketing, product is define into Core Product : What your audience wants in exchange for performing the behavior), Actual Product (major tangible goods or services that will be promoted and any special product features) , Augmented Product (Additional tangible goods or services that might make it more likely will adopt the behavior).

Price

Price is the cost that the audience associates with adopting the desired behavior. In social marketing framework, adoption cost define into monetary and nonmonetary benefits. Monetary benefits are most often related to goods or services associated with adopting behavior. While non- monetary are more intangible and often more significant for social marketing products (consist of time, effort, energy) that are required to perform the behavior.

According to the survey that was conducted, 40% respondents were likely to receive rewards that were provided by Reblood. They said the rewards are interesting and useful. Reblood needs to maintain and keep the reward program in order to retain their users and acquire new users. Following strategy could help Reblood to improve their loyalty program .

Monetary Benefits:

- Increase variant of rewards, combining digital rewards (pulsa, e-voucher, etc) and physical rewards (household appliance, kitchen set, etc)
- Implement tiering mechanism based on blood donors frequency. Benefits will follow tiering, the higher tiering, the higher point and reward that user gets.
- Collaborate with merchant to give reward (discount or special price)
- Provide mission or challenge gamification to reach some sort of goal (i.e consume healthy food for a month) and give rewards when challenge accomplished.

Non-monetary Benefits:

- Provide wall of appreciation or leader board to appreciate Reblood's user based on their blood donor routine
- Give education rewards (i.e consultation to the expert, counselling, free webinar access, etc)
- Provide feature that able user to share their activity to social media for the awareness and recognize
- Invites some of Reblood users to be a part of Reblood campaign and gather all users to be part of Reblood community

Place

Place in social marketing is where and when the audiences will perform the desired behavior and receive any associated services. In order to acquire more audiences to do blood donors and more active users using Reblood application. Several improvement regarding place: Launch iOS application as soon as possible to provide apple users, Improve app's performance, Manage and maintain big data to gets more insight , Connect with many more PMI to make system automate and centralized.

Promotion

Currently, Reblood's promotion strategy happens in social media such as Instagram, twitter, and facebook. Reblood's media content are mostly dominated with blood donation's event and schedule, repost for blood urgently needed and information from PMI. The user engagement is not as much since the content is quite monotone. Hence, some improvement is required in order to gain blood donors and increasing number of Reblood active's users. In this research, the author is adopting Brand Generated Content (BGC) and User generated Content (UGC). BGC is type of communication which the company carefully create to demonstrate business value in order to influence and encourage audiences to use the product (Mangold, 2009). While UGC is content that produced by online users to create engagement or lead a conversation. It could be find in product review, podcast, video, photo, etc (Vries, S. d., & Olsson, 2015).

CONCLUSION

Based on analysis, there are several factors that influence audience decision to donate their blood, motivational and barrier. Motivation factors that audience share and think it would adopt the desired behavior is dominating by Humanitarian action, implementing healthy lifestyle, 911 situation, and rewards or incentive that offered after donate blood. On the other hand, some barriers factors that also influence audience doubt to donor are health concern, fear of contagion, fear of pain of needles, and bad experience on previous blood donation. Through those factors, Reblood should create marketing campaign that refers to those motivation and barriers factors to increase engagement with the users and acquire more new user. So that, number of blood donation in Indonesia could be increase or at least fulfil our blood needs.

In order to create successful social marketing campaign that precise with target audience which is young generation, Reblood should set its target goals, belief, and behaviour objective of their audience based on internal and external analysis. Hence, behaviour objective that would like to achieve are define into three stage: Dormant/ Never donor, First timer, repeat / loyal user. To develop successful social marketing campaign, Reblood proposed to follow the social marketing plan start from select the target audience that ready to action and have the potential market segment, it is better to approach young generation refers to the demographic bonus that experienced in Indonesia currently. Once target audience has been define as well with those factors that could change audience behavior, it is important to develop the positioning statement in order to create social campaign program, for instance: "Reblood is an app to help people build healthy lifestyle and saving lives, starting with blood donation".

Develop social marketing Mix 4Ps is also the important, by defining Reblood products into core, actual, and augmented makes it easier to planning the social campaign. Provide monetary benefits likes improve the rewards variance, give discount to selected merchant and non- monetary benefits like give educational rewards, share user's activities, and conduct the sharing session with the experts could helps Reblood to acquire more active users and retain their loyal one. Other than that, enhance application performance is also needed, launch iOS application as soon as possible to reach other segment of user and the last is deciding on messages, creative strategies, and communication channel that suitable with the young generation as the target users.

LIMITATION & FURTHER RESEARCH

This research scope and limitation only covers Jawa Timur and DKI Jakarta areas. Further research should be expand to others area in Indonesia. Future research could be consider the correlation between motivation, barriers and knowledge in order to planning more precise social marketing campaign program.

REFERENCES

1. BPS. (2021). *Hasil Sensus Penduduk 2020*.
2. Enis B.M. (1974). Marketing Principles: The Management Process. In *Marketing Principles: The Management Process* (p. 228).
3. Essel, S. M. (2018). Motivational factors for blood donation, potential barriers, and knowledge about blood donation in first-time and repeat blood donors. *BMC Hematol 2018 Dec 20;18:36. doi: 10.1186/s12878-018-0130-3. eCollection 2018*.
4. Hastings, G. and Domegan, C. (2014). Social Marketing: From Tunes to Symphonies. 2nd ed. In *Social Marketing: From Tunes to Symphonies. 2nd ed* (p. 14).
5. Indonesia, P. M. (2020). *Annual Report 2020*.
6. Kotler and Keller (2006). Marketing Management. 12th Edition. In *Marketing Management. 12th Edition* (p. 50).
7. Mangold, W. G. (2009). Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix. In *Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix* (pp. 357-365.).
8. Nancy R. Lee, Michael L. Rothschild, and Bill Smith. (2011). Social Marketing Influencing Behaviors for Good. In *Social Marketing Influencing Behaviors for Good* (p. 7).
9. Philip Kotler and Nancy R.Lee. (2020). Social Marketing : Behavior Change for Social Good 6th edition. In *Social Marketing : Behavior Change for Social Good 6th edition* (p. 55).
10. Prochaska, J. O., & DiClemente, C. C. (1982). Transtheoretical therapy: Toward a more integrative model of change. In *Transtheoretical therapy: Toward a more integrative model of change*.

11. Rothaermel, F. T. (2013). Strategic management : concepts and cases. In *Strategic management : concepts and cases* (p. 91).
12. Stephen S. Holden and Damian Cox. (2013). Social marketing : immunizing against unethical practice. In S. S. Cox, *Social marketing : immunizing against unethical practice* (p. 59).
13. The Jakarta Post. (2021). *Hunting for Blood*. Retrieved from The Jakarta Post: <https://www.thejakartapost.com/life/2021/01/13/hunting-for-blood.html>
14. Vries, S. d., & Olsson. (2015). The usage of consumer generated advertising and its effect on receives attitude. *Master Thesis, Linnaeus University*.
15. Wei Pan, L. C. (2019). PESTEL Analysis of Construction Productivity Enhancement Strategies: A Case Study of Three Economies. *Journal of Management in Engineering* 35(1):5018013 DOI:10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000662.

Cite this Article: Putu Linda Primandari Ambarini, Iriawan Ibarat (2022). Proposed Social Marketing Campaign to Increase Blood Donation and Active Users in Reblood Application (Case Study: PT Gaya Hidup Sehat). International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(5), 1646-1653